

Inspiring the Next Generation of Geospatial Experts

McKee A^{*1}, Edwards S^{†1}, Mills H^{‡1},

¹Newcastle University

January 16, 2022

Summary

A new website, Geospatial UK, has been created to address an expected skills shortage across the geospatial sector, focusing on how geospatial can be more widely and easily introduced within education to create a broader awareness of the sector as a potential career pathway. Through working closely with both industry stakeholders and teachers across different education setting and levels, this website hopes to increase the use of the term geospatial within education and thus create a stronger awareness of the sector for those making career decisions.

KEYWORDS: geospatial, GIS, education, curriculum, skills shortage

1. Background

The geospatial sector is currently valued in the UK annually at £11 billion (Cabinet Office, 2018) and is expected to continue grow further. The importance of the sector is such that in 2018 the government established the Geospatial Commission, with the role of setting the UK's geospatial strategy and promoting the sector more widely. Despite this, it's predicted there will a be significant shortfall of suitably qualified geospatial experts within 10 to 20 years, leaving a significant skills shortage in the wider sector and a high demand for potential employees. The potential impact of this across the industry, from construction services, to data management and geospatial analysis could have significant consequences with roles left unfilled and business looking internationally to solve this problem.

So why are there so few geospatially skilled employees, despite record-high levels of demand in an £11 billion annual industry in the UK? Recent research published in The State of Geospatial Survey Education (CICES, 2019) suggests that the reduced rate of recruitment is due to the lack of awareness of the geospatial sector at primary and secondary school level. However, GIS (Geographic Information Systems) is a compulsory component of the national curriculum in England and Wales, with students across geography expected to be aware of GIS, if not have access to use GIS software themselves. This highlights a lack of knowledge or time for geospatial, and in-particular, GIS, to be taught and covered at school, despite specifically being required under national curriculums.

The remainder of this paper addresses the research undertaken, working with teachers to understand issues with covering geospatial in the classroom, and the outcomes of this, including the development of a set of resources aimed to help increase awareness of the geospatial sector as a career pathway from secondary school level.

2. Research methodology

Two approaches were adopted to understand the barriers to teaching GIS in schools, as is required as part of the curriculum (i) a workshop and (ii) two surveys. Initially, a workshop (i) was held with a small set of teachers from a range of backgrounds, levels, and expertise in GIS to gather (a) information

* Alex.mckee@newcastle.ac.uk

† stuart.edwards@newcastle.ac.uk

‡ henny.mills@newcastle.ac.uk

on their own GIS knowledge, (b) the wider knowledge within their school, (c) what were the barriers to teaching GIS, and (d) what useful resources would help address these problems.

Then a survey (ii) was circulated around a wide-ranging set of teachers with responses collected covering areas such as ‘What exam board do you teach?’, ‘In your opinion, which KS5 topics do you think have a good fit with GIS?’, and ‘What other resources, if any, would you like available for KS5?’. A second survey was distributed to undergraduate students at Newcastle University enrolled on Geospatial Engineering courses to understand why there is a lack of understanding in schools of what geospatial engineering is, including degree options, and why they chose their current degree programme.

3. Results

The results of the workshop highlighted the barriers to using GIS in the classroom which are summarised in **Figure 1**. Barriers included difficulty understanding available GIS data, lack of access to software due to either finances, experience or administration access, lack of time available to complete longer exercises, difficulty finding GIS exercises which linked to the curriculum, and additional difficulties teaching during COVID-19 lockdowns as students worked from home and could not be as carefully supervised, and no external GIS experts could be invited into schools.

Figure 1 Barriers to using GIS in the classroom.

The results of the survey circulated among teachers showed that the majority of Geography teachers rated their own GIS skills quite poorly (**Figure 2**), with over 85% rating their GIS skills as a ‘3 out of 5’ or below. Additionally, it was discovered that teachers who rated their GIS skills as a ‘1 out of 5’ were unable to see how GIS could link to the curriculum at all, while those who rated their skills higher were able to suggest multiple applications for GIS in the curriculum. 94% of all respondents stated that they required GIS support in the form of either CPD course, tutorial video or handbook. A further 27% believed that free software and guidance would improve their ability to teach GIS in the classroom.

Figure 2 Results from the survey circulated among secondary school Geography teachers.

The results of the survey distributed to undergraduate students at Newcastle University enrolled on Geospatial Engineering courses showed that only 35% were aware of the term ‘geospatial’ while at school, whereas 55% were aware of the term ‘GIS’ while at school. Further investigation indicates that this higher rate of recognition is due to GIS being promoted to a compulsory component of the national curriculum in England and Wales in 2014. In response to the question, ‘How did you find out about your course while at school (for example, career day, university outreach talks, staff came to visit, prospectus, etc.)?’ 5% of respondents answered that they chose their current degree programme because they had learned GIS at school. A further 15% said that they chose GIS because their teacher previously studied it, highlighting again the impact of a teacher’s ability to use GIS on a student’s learning.

Figure 3 Results from the survey distributed to undergraduate students at Newcastle University enrolled on Geospatial Engineering courses.

4. Outcomes

A new website has been created called Geospatial UK, aimed at KS4 and KS5 (16 – 18-year-old) students who enjoy geography, maps, being outdoors or about using technology to understand data (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Home page of new website.

It also includes a range of geospatially themed classroom activities (**Figure 5**), formed from the feedback gained from the initial workshop (i) and survey circulated among teachers (ii). All topics link to the Geography curriculum and each activity teaches students a new skill, for example, creating heat maps or importing a CSV file. Each activity is designed to take approximately 30 – 45 minutes to complete, so that they can be finished in one teaching period. The activities also make use of free, accessible software and datasets, to remove some of the barriers preventing teachers from using GIS in classrooms. Furthermore, the activities are collated into one PDF document, which both reduces the amount of complicated or difficult-to-access GIS data, and allows students to complete the activity at home if required due to COVID restrictions.

Figure 5 Some of the designed GIS exercise that align to the Geography curriculum.

Additional pages on the website include information about the wide range of careers in the geospatial sector, including job descriptions and pay, as well as highlighting opportunities such as work experience or competitions. There is a dedicated page for teachers where they can find guidance and support on improving their own GIS skills including free activities to help deliver curriculum-led geospatial lessons, and opportunities for in-school or virtual workshop sessions with a geospatial expert.

The new Geospatial UK website was launched in June 2021 and has already received an overwhelmingly positive response from both industry and educators.

“One of the best things I have seen to promote the profession in years.” *Barry Gleeson, Wood Plc*

“The website is pitched at the right level and offers excellent insight into the career paths available.” *Nicki Nichols, The Hydrographic Society Scotland*

“The website looks great and will be a great portal to support our industry.” *Colin Murphy, Murphy Geospatial*

“I’ve been going through the activities myself over the last couple of days and I’m blown away. I cannot wait to introduce these to my students.” *Alex Carter, Geography Teacher at The John Roan School*

5. Conclusions

The project, Geospatial UK, has been undertaken to address an expected skills shortage across the geospatial sector, focusing on how geospatial can be more widely and easily introduced within education to create a broader awareness of the sector as a potential career pathway. Through working closely with both industry stakeholders and teachers across different education setting and levels, a new website has been launched hoping to help address the problems identified and increase the use of the term geospatial within education and thus create a stronger awareness of the sector for those making career decisions.

The next steps for the Geospatial UK project are to promote the website, workshops and resources available in order to raise further awareness of the geospatial sector among KS4 and KS5 students in order to boost the recruitment pipeline and rejuvenate the sector.

6. Acknowledgements

Many thanks to the supporters and partners of the project - Hexagon, Leica Geosystems, RICS, bp, The Hydrographic Society UK & Ireland, KOREC Group, Plowman Craven, Murphy Geospatial, Malcolm Hughes and Survey Solutions

References

Cabinet Office (2018) An Initial Analysis of the Potential Geospatial Economic Opportunity.

Available at:

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/733864/Initial_Analysis_of_the_Potential_Geospatial_Economic_Opportunity.pdf [Accessed: 17/01/22].

Chartered Institution of Civil Engineering Surveyors (2019) State of Geospatial Survey Education.

Biographies

Alex McKee is an Outreach Officer at Newcastle University working with the Geospatial Engineering department to inspire the next generation of geospatial experts. Graduated in BSc Geography. Industry experience of Land and Building Surveying, before returning to the university to highlight geospatial careers for geographically minded students.

Professor Stuart Edwards is currently working in the role of Dean & CEO NUIS (Singapore). Discipline related research interests focus on Engineering Geodesy and in particular low-cost systems for precise monitoring of engineering structures and Earth processes (including ice-mass balance in Greenland), GNSS quality indicators and satellite altimetry.

Dr Henny Mills is Degree Programme Director for Surveying and Mapping Science and Geographic Information Science at Newcastle University. Main areas of expertise related to research are remote

sensing, in particular Artificial Neural Networks and Support Vector Machines for the processing of high spatial resolution imagery, surveying and e-learning.